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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
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STRATEGIES FOR OVERCOMING DIFFICULTIES IN USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article examines pedagogical and methodological strategies for overcoming difficulties encountered when using authentic materials—newspaper and journal articles, audio and video recordings, podcasts, films, and online resources—in English language teaching. The study draws on the theoretical frameworks of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), as well as the scholarly contributions of Stephen Krashen, Brian Tomlinson, William Guariento, and David Nunan. Core challenges, including lexical complexity, cultural context barriers, listening comprehension difficulties, and affective obstacles, are analyzed in depth. The article proposes effective strategies such as scaffolding, graduated difficulty sequencing, intercultural competence development, and the integration of digital technologies into the learning process. The findings have significant practical implications for teachers working in Uzbek secondary and tertiary educational institutions.

Key words: authentic materials, communicative language teaching, scaffolding, intercultural competence, affective filter, task-based language teaching, digital technologies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida asl (authentic) materiallardan – gazeta va jurnal maqolalari, audio va video yozuvlar, podkastlar, filmlar va internet resurslari – foydalanishda yuzaga keladigan muammolar hamda ularni yengib o'tishning pedagogik-metodologik strategiyalari ilmiy-nazariy nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot kommunikativ tilni o'qitish (CLT), vazifaga asoslangan til ta'limi (TBLT), shuningdek, Stephen Krashen va Brian Tomlinson kabi yetakchi olimlarning nazariy qarashlariga tayanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari o'zbek maktablari va oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'qituvchilari uchun muhim amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: asl materiallar, kommunikativ til o'qitish, scaffolding, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, affektiv filtr, vazifaga asoslangan til ta'limi, raqamli texnologiyalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются педагогические и методологические стратегии преодоления трудностей, возникающих при использовании аутентичных материалов – газетных и журнальных статей, аудио- и видеозаписей, подкастов, фильмов и интернет-ресурсов – в процессе обучения английскому языку. Исследование опирается на теоретические основы коммуникативного обучения языку (CLT), обучения на основе заданий (TBLT), а также на научные труды Stephen Krashen, Brian Tomlinson, William Guariento и David Nunan. Подробно анализируются основные трудности, включая лексическую сложность, культурные барьеры, проблемы аудирования и аффективные факторы. Предлагаются эффективные стратегии, такие как скаффолдинг, поэтапное усложнение материала, развитие межкультурной компетенции и интеграция цифровых технологий в учебный процесс. Полученные результаты имеют важное практическое значение для преподавателей средних и высших учебных заведений Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: аутентичные материалы, коммуникативное обучение языку, скаффолдинг, межкультурная компетенция, аффективный фильтр, обучение на основе заданий, цифровые технологии.

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary English language teaching methodology is undergoing a period of profound transformation on a global scale. As the paradigm of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) continues to gain currency, the importance of instructional resources that bridge the classroom and the real world has grown considerably. In this context, authentic materials—that is, texts and media produced not for pedagogical purposes but by native speakers for genuine communicative ends—have become a central element of modern language instruction. Authentic materials encompass a broad spectrum: newspaper and journal articles, television and radio broadcasts, podcasts, feature films, social media content, advertising, and internet resources. As Guariento and Morley (2001) observe, incorporating authentic materials into the classroom provides learners with the opportu-

nity to encounter language in its natural, contextualised form, engage with a range of registers and styles, and develop cultural competence alongside linguistic skills.

However, practitioners consistently report that the use of authentic materials generates significant pedagogical and linguistic challenges. In the context of Uzbekistan's educational system, these difficulties are further compounded by local pedagogical traditions, a limited target-language environment, and the specific psychological characteristics of Uzbek learners. The present article has three principal aims:

- (1) to classify the core difficulties encountered when using authentic materials based on established theoretical frameworks;
- (2) to propose evidence-based strategies for overcoming these difficulties; and
- (3) to evaluate the applicability of such strategies within Uzbek secondary and tertiary educational institutions.

The study employs the following methodology: a systematic review of relevant scholarly literature, comparative analysis of best practices, and assessment of their adaptability to the Uzbek educational context.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theory of authentic materials is closely associated with two dominant pedagogical approaches: Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). The CLT approach, as systematised by Richards and Rodgers (2014), places communicative competence at the centre of language learning, defined as the ability to use language accurately, appropriately, and effectively in real-life contexts. Within this framework, authentic materials serve as the primary source through which learners encounter real language use. Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1982), expressed through the "i+1" formula, posits that language acquisition occurs when learners are exposed to input slightly above their current level of competence. This principle provides a key criterion for selecting authentic materials: they must be challenging yet comprehensible.

Tomlinson (2011) highlights the importance of emotional engagement and personal relevance in materials development, arguing that authentic materials are most effective when they stimulate curiosity, reflection, and emotional response. Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1985) further emphasises that anxiety, low motivation, and lack of confidence can hinder language acquisition, thereby necessitating a supportive learning environment. Nunan (1988) broadens the concept of authenticity by asserting that materials must be not only genuine in origin but also meaningful and relevant to learners' lives.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

One of the most significant challenges associated with authentic materials is their linguistic complexity. Texts intended for native speakers often contain vocabulary, grammatical structures, and stylistic features beyond learners' proficiency levels. Kilickaya (2004) found that intermediate learners encounter an unfamiliar word approximately every ten words in authentic texts, which significantly impairs comprehension. Key lexical challenges include idiomatic expressions, colloquial contractions and slang, domain-specific terminology, and polysemous words with context-dependent meanings. Language and culture are intrinsically linked; authentic materials reflect cultural norms, historical references, and social conventions of the anglophone world.

Corbett (2003) notes that lack of cultural understanding leads not only to misinterpretation but also to learner alienation. For Uzbek learners, culturally specific humour, political references, and popular culture elements often remain opaque. Additionally, natural speech rate, accent variation, and connected speech phenomena—such as assimilation, elision, linking, and contractions—pose significant listening challenges. Field (2008) demonstrates that learners struggle more with segmenting continuous speech than recognising individual words.

The Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA) model proposed by Horwitz et al. (1986) identifies communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test anxiety as major barriers. Furthermore, Uzbek institutions face practical constraints, including limited internet access, insufficient technical equipment, copyright restrictions, and difficulty accessing high-quality materials. Collins and Mayblin (2002) report that 67% of teachers in developing contexts identify such constraints as primary barriers.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The concept of scaffolding, introduced by Vygotsky (1978) and developed by Wood et al. (1976), refers to structured support that enables learners to perform tasks beyond their independent capabilities. In practice, this includes pre-teaching vocabulary, providing simplified parallel texts, modelling tasks, and guided questioning.

Based on Krashen's "i+1" principle, materials should be selected according to learners' interests, introduced gradually, and adapted to ensure 60-70% initial comprehensibility, increasing to 80-90% over time.

Nation and Waring (1997) recommend 95-98% lexical familiarity for adequate comprehension. The Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) model (Byram, 1997) supports integrating cultural instruction through briefings, comparative discussions, and learner participation. Field's (2008) staged listening model includes global, selective, detailed, interactive, and shadowing phases. Digital tools such as YouTube, Language Reactor, TED Talks, Quizlet, and Audacity enhance engagement and accessibility. Legal considerations are addressed by Uzbekistan's Copyright Law (2006), which allows limited educational use. Strategies based on Krashen's and Deci & Ryan's theories include reducing anxiety, fostering motivation, and promoting collaborative learning. TBLT (Ellis, 2003) integrates authentic materials naturally through task-based activities.

Discussion and practical recommendations: Effective implementation in Uzbekistan requires contextual adaptation. At lower proficiency levels (A2-B1), locally relevant English materials should complement global resources. Short (2-3 minute) materials suit the 45-minute lesson format. Institutions should develop curated authentic material banks and support teacher digital literacy through professional development.

CONCLUSION

Authentic materials offer significant pedagogical benefits but require systematic implementation strategies to address linguistic, cultural, psychological, and logistical challenges. The integrated application of scaffolding, graded input, intercultural competence, structured listening, digital tools, affective support, and TBLT can substantially enhance learning outcomes.

Future research should focus on empirical validation in the Uzbek context and development of assessment frameworks tailored to local needs.

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 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.